

Political Violence: Some Critical Reflections

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Abstract:

All violence is now understood as political violence. Understanding violence is always a monumental task owing to the fact that different kinds of violence vary from time to time, and its various definitions do not encompass all the nuances of violence that we face and see today. Going through different definitions of violence indicates a lack of clarity. We keep trying to analyze the nature of violence, but it remains a puzzle. We owe this confusion to rapidly changing political scenarios, but none of them are able to foster radical diversity and radical difference; in other words, radical democracy. This paper, emphasizes the requisiteness of an expanding circle of reference from larger states of exception to permanent states of exception. We also have to look at a causal relationship between the two even to begin answering our pressing concerns about the human condition.

Keywords: Violence, Everyday, Permanent Exception, Radical

The specter of violence is haunting us as we live in the supposedly post-ideological, post-communist, and post-political age. In several works on the political philosophy of violence, the radical nature of violence is brought forth, exposing or characterizing it as extraordinary violence, only to be characterized as “Radical Evil”. In this analysis of [extraordinary] violence, the principal reference has been the Holocaust (more than the genocidal violence outside of the field of Europe, whether Asia, Africa, or Latin America), where one finds a one-dimensional interpretation of it - be it anti-metaphysics, anti-foundational politics, or anti-ideological politics. Saying so the paper is only concerned about the expansive horizon of thinking about violence and the human condition. The arguments that follow strictly convey that the point of reference makes a difference – the violence ‘elsewhere’ is as deplorable as violence ‘here’. This paper claims that there is already a profound reflection on violence and the human condition available in the philosophical literature on violence and politics. However, there is a limitation here. The limitation is the observational element in our critical reflection of violence. It implies that the ground of the argument requires a change in focus from the usual indicators of violence. One such possibility can be drawn from Agamben’s point of “exception becoming the rule.” Alongside exceptional scenarios understanding of violence requires a significant focus on various normalizations of everyday life. These normalizations have the potential to cause the systemic violence.

A universal definition of violence and an universal critique of the human condition is always relevant as long as there are wars, genocides and political crimes. Undoubtedly, the eruption of such violence draws us to the great admonishment of human reason and the human condition. Referring to Martin Beck

Matustik¹ and Tracy Strong² immediately takes us back to discovering various causal determinants of violence. They resemble a particular mode of analysis peculiar to certain political philosophers who consciously or unconsciously seem to measure only specific historical facts as proofs of human perversion. Their perceptions of violence indicate that they are well aware of the paradigms denounced, *i.e.*, Western metaphysics ([political] foundationalism), and paradigms embraced, *i.e.*, politics without banisters ([political] anti-foundationalism). This approach to understand violence indicates the cacophony of the Western world's attempt at the remorseful attitude to the "possibility of evil" (Arendt's way). What is the result of this? The consequence of it is the distortion of history itself. Much of the critical reflections of Western thinkers could be summarized like this: there is a smooth flow of time and space with intermittent intersections and interventions of systemic violence in the form of mass murders. Everyone knows these are committed in the name of conformity to the ideology rooted in the normalized live of those cultures and societies. To put it more candidly, the assumption of violence and dehumanization confined to specific systemic violence is to view it in a constricted sense. The condition that gave rise to a particularly violent ideology compels us to grasp its contradictions. Comprehending the 'fall of the human' this way is like what Zizek refers to as subjective violence - identification even in the arbitrary sense/of the perpetrator, agent, or action³.

Expanding the understanding of political violence to vast forms of its latentness, we need to look at objective violence – with no apparent perpetrator or agent. It implies that the ontology of violence differs from that of the human condition. When does it happen? The possibility of everyday violence directs our attention to objective violence – where it lies symbolically or happens to be the ground of the symbolic order. Richard Bernstein directs our attention to this aspect of violence while referring to thinking without banisters. The objective violence aligns with Agamben's notion of "exception becoming the rule."⁴ The symbolic order or the ground (giving it a psychoanalytic sense) is bound to give rise to those eruptions of systemic violence. It exposes our current fragile ground of the human condition, constituted by more corrupted by civil, cultural and political spheres and orders. It also exposes the spectrality of violence seen in the Hobbesian philosophy of natural violence. It does not disappear; instead, it is the manifestation of extraordinary forms. Natural violence in social conditions sounds more dangerous to us.

The distinction between ordinary and extraordinary violence, and between subjective and objective violence lies in our very understanding of the past and its bearing on us regarding its knowledge and its justifications. Civilizational conflicts, cultural antagonisms, religious differences, political and ideological differences, and violence place the vulnerable and the accountable before us. The issue of identifying the guilty party is as futile as faulting the human nature. This is a strange paradox we have to work with – the flaw in the human character makes violence ontological and a historical analysis makes its concrete. Moral blameworthiness is also built into the order of our thinking and judgment. The culture of blame, like the satanic aspect of evil where good a God will take care of the faithful, is confined to the subjective interpretation of violence. In this mode of thinking and searching for the sacrificial lamb, there

¹ Beck Matustik, Martin. *Radical Evil and Impossible Hope: Post Secular Meditations*, Indianapolis: Indiana University Press, 2008.

² Strong, Tracy B. *Politics without Vision: Thinking without a Banister in the Twentieth Century*, New York: The University of Chicago Press, 2012.

³ Zizek, Slavoj, *Violence*. New York: Picador, 2008. p. 9.

⁴ "Law encompasses living beings" Agamben, Giorgio. *Homo Sacer: Sovereign, Power and Bare Life*. Stanford University Press, 1998. p. 3.

seems to be precise figuration and demarcation between the perpetrator and the redeemer. Bringing everything to subjective violence makes us identify the human condition's good, bad, and ugly elements. Can objective violence really pinpoint or identify the culprit? Is it all right to bring objective violence to the understanding of everyday life? To answer these questions, we need to take a position on the nature of the critique of violence in Western political philosophy. Its reflection on violence and the human condition is profound as far as systemic violence is concerned. Even in the case of Hannah Arendt, evil and violence are given serious concern only in the context of the Holocaust. The complaint is that transcendent metaphysics supports elitist politics. Taking such a position does not imply an underestimation of the event. Questioning the ways of the critique and remembering the event distort our thinking and political imagination, as well as a different coloring of the past. Twentieth-century violence is seen as the pinnacle moment of perversion and inhumanity. We can raise two questions: How did Western metaphysical foundationalism cause violence? Second, is there any misunderstanding in blaming metaphysics for all the violence? There are no simple answers to these questions. Making metaphysics accountable is only a half-reality. The other guilty party here is human nature and its easy propensity for inhuman acts. There is no doubt about the dehumanizing and perverse nature of violence that preceded and succeeded the Holocaust. More than fighting foundationalism we are supposed to defeat its multifarious forms and impressions in our everyday life. Everyday life is a pure reflection of our attitudes, mindsets and valuations we extend to several manifestations of the other.

Violence under the conditions of post-foundationalism and post-metaphysics challenges the validity of criticisms of metaphysics and western philosophy. The violence that followed the collapse of the socialist experiment throws us into even greater moral quandaries. These facts compel us to doubt our moral strength to live together with radical differences and political conviction to preserve these differences. The critique of metaphysics has two aspects: politics without foundations and a departure from metaphysics. There is some opposition to political truth here. The shift to post-metaphysics or post-foundations shifted our focus from systemic references to everyday forms of normalized violence. Times have changed since Hannah Arendt. There are two notable ones: one, the emergence of post-communism, referred to as the flourishing of democracy, and the other, post-secularism; which also brought about the former's decline. These changes are characteristic of the change not only in our conception of politics but also in the violence present in even more complex forms. The change that would interest us is the location of subjective violence in the symbolic order of objective violence. Normalized exceptions or permanent emergencies give a different picture of the political and social order. Agamben's suppositions greatly influenced later political theorists, and such ideas were also seen in the writings of Badiou, Mouffe, Laclau, Nancy, Ranciere and Esposito. One more distinction is to be made here before we proceed further. The fundamental violence in the order of life (the Hobbesian way) somewhat differs from the political violence within the political order. Whereas the former is more of a struggle to remain alive, the latter manifests in many different avatars in political society owing to the dynamics of power. The onslaught on metaphysics dismantled the idea of absolute truth that was supposed to shape the political realm. Two clarifications are made here. The catastrophic nature of subjective violence is attributed to metaphysics and the ontological status of violence to the post-metaphysical condition. Several claims came into force to justify the emphasis on everyday forms of violence in terms of normative rules. The latter is constitutive of the historical continuities hampering a cordial relationship between freedom, equality, and justice, besides newer manifestations and incarnations to sustain these historical continuities. This provides a clear understanding of the world's reluctance toward justice and equality. Perpetration of violence speaks

volumes about this reluctance and our non-committal attitude to realize these principles strongly defeated by vulgar display of power.

The preservation of life is at stake in an unevenly frightening manner in the implicit terms of dominance. This is a contestable inference. An identifiable difference between ontological and metaphysical violence would be interesting. Any critique of violence has to shed some serious light on the fundamental nature of violence - the state of power. We are entirely wrong if we assume that we have done away with the fundamentality of violence. However, political violence is more than ontological violence grounded in specific forms of harm and injury. Our desire to achieve reasonable standards of equality and justice is met with strong opposition to these ideals. This has always been our primary concern. War and terror are instances of exceptions and catastrophic times. Moreover, extra emphasis on catastrophic times and judging the human condition points to the distinction between punishable (redeemable) violence (symbolic and structural) and violence beyond moral judgment. Human tenacity for perverse violence is also an issue of non-moral nature of the problem of social consciousness. We can evaluate 'the political' from the point of view of the judgment of others in the collective lives of individuals. The judgment of others is something to be taken very seriously. In the condition of a "state of war" or a "state of violence," we cannot say with certainty that violence is the outcome of the judgment of others. Why do individuals falter in their judgment of others in the social world? We must remind ourselves that Kant was very confident in this possibility *via* the categorical imperative and the mediation of moral laws. Hobbesian fundamental violent condition of nature is resolved with Kantian morality. Some of this kind is seen in the works of Rousseau and Marx - the tackling of natural inequalities and social inequalities.

How had metaphysics caused [political] violence? How does metaphysics negatively affect and destroy the sanity of the world? The failure of political sanity is attributed to the ill effects of metaphysics. Take any instance of twentieth-century violence (any crime against humanity); what kind of metaphysical drive is found in the occurrence of any of those catastrophic events? Sundar Sarukkai's discussion of the suspicion of metaphysics towards any political action is attractive⁵. Such an approach is very evident in Tracy Strong's *Politics Without Vision*. To answer these questions, we must reflect on Arendt's critical reflection of the *banality of evil*, focusing on thinking, being, willing, and judging. In doing so, we will gain insight into the necessity of "thinking without banisters" (in one way to be labelled as post-foundationalism) especially for politics and political theory. First, what is foundationalism in political theory? Arthur Ripstein provides an exciting account: "understanding a particular political order or imagining it without grounding it in any substantive assumptions - which holds up an edifice without itself being supported by anything else."⁶ Suspicion of metaphysics or excessive wonder is what Arendt firmly intended to avoid. Alleging metaphysics is something to be taken more seriously. This argument comes to our aid - "Hobbes seeks to demonstrate the acceptability of particular arrangements by showing that it would be rational for people to agree to conform to them."⁷

The necessity of a rational political order follows Hobbes' hypothetical (rather rhetorical) account of the natural state as the state of war. Hobbes might have assumed that violence's ontological nature is avoided

⁵ Sarukkai, Sundar, 'Is Metaphysics Political?', in Vinay Lal, and Roby Rajan (eds), *India and the Unthinkable: Backwaters Collective on Metaphysics and Politics* (Delhi, 2016; online edn, Oxford Academic, 17 Nov. 2016), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199466863.003.0001>, accessed 21 Sep. 2022.

⁶ Ripstein, Arthur, *Foundationalism in Political Theory* (August 19, 1987). *Philosophy and Public Affairs*, Vol. 16, No. 2, Spring 1987, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1238357>. P. 115.

⁷ Ripstein, Arthur, *Foundationalism in Political Theory*, p. 115.

or overcome by creating a rationalized commonwealth with all powers under the sovereign authority. Individuals do not remain as mere *bios* [bare life] in the social condition – to connect it to the Arendtian notion of ways to understand the individual as a political being-in-the-world. This is important where individuals indulge in extraordinary ways or means of organizing into incommunicable identities. Incommunicability comes from incompatible values and dispositions that are radically diverse and aversive to commonality. There is an anthropological element to it besides political reasons. Our inability to come together with radical differences points out the failure of the politicization process. Politics is always an unfinished project because of the difference between the social and the political. This situation keeps the human associational aspect ever-perplexing. The pressing issue in contemporary times is one's reluctance to live with the *radical other*, or in other words, with radical differences. This reluctance is accompanied by her easy subjection to provocations to antagonisms and hate. Arendt's concern is "how do individuals relate to others?"⁸ - remains yet to be answered. Individuals are neither mere biological entities nor multiple duplications of sameness. Instead, they are profound embodiments of radical differences symbolic of radically incompatible others (like Levinas's thinking of the other as an *infinite* other). However, forming political and social orders is not seen as an impossible task. They are always seen as problematic and contentious, and they are never finished. This seems to be the point of fear where individuals with multiple identities concerning religion, community, ethnicity, and ideology often find it challenging to share the same social space. This fear has given rise to intolerance everywhere, of 'which I cannot make sense of,' thus causing violence everywhere and creating the condition of a permanent emergency.

We need to understand normalized violence in light of the thinking and judging that Arendt was greatly concerned with. Thoughtlessness may be the attribute of "unprecedented violence," while the same attribute does not go well with normalized violence (suppression and oppression). The latter is consciously carried out and thoughtfully executed by fellow human beings. While doing so, persons acting violently disregard and infringe on all aspects of dignity and self-respect deemed morally inalienable for everyone. That thinking refrains us from committing any morally abhorrent action, individual or collective, is just an overestimation of our moral capacities. On the contrary, everyday normalizations – major among them being 'violence is normal owing to its ontological status - are a proof of irreconcilable differences. For instance, India has an unmanageable complex diversity that is both fragile and robust. Its diversity is predominantly measured by the nature of the political system it has from time to time. However, the shaping of the political realm and politics here are controlled by 'historical-cultural' factors. Justifying historically-sanctioned social hierarchy (supposed as 'never to be levelled') hinders political reconciliation of these *deep-rooted* differences. Time and again, this reluctance to live together with radicalized differences resulted in the never-ending vulnerability of a substantial section of society to physical violence and pathological subservience. In some sense, to modify Arendt's thesis, thoughtlessness is endemic to human existence, where moral valuations are drawn on whatever dispositions we hold. Here, the point is to argue that both systemic violence and violence by the 'normalized exception' are carried out conscientiously to perpetuate a particular mode of dominant hierarchy. This thoughtlessness is *ever present* and indicative of a failure of conscience, resulting in violence that "stains the globe." It also seriously puts to utter disbelief our ability to 'overcome the given' picture of the human condition. Thoughtlessness is also located in the dominant tendencies of unquestionable categories of existence.

⁸ Tracy B. Strong, *Politics Without Vision*, p. 300.

Actions of failed conscience in extraordinary situations do not only distort the everyday.⁹ On the contrary, failure to be human, even in ordinary situations, leads to those extraordinary failures we keep talking about. Political catastrophes and other historical accounts can be seen in this light. Everyday sounds a lot more terrifying after the terror, even if we keep asserting that extraordinary failures fail us every day in every aspect of togetherness.

Everyday life is characterized by acts of distrust. The capacity to think directs our ability to judge our actions as right and wrong. There are other scenarios, too, where individuals are cognizant of moral wrongs yet do not care about these moral wrongs. Arendt's idea can be mentioned here. Everyday life is characterized by such moral wrongs as attaining an amoral sense. This has caused the anaesthetization of politics and difficulty responding to or tackling every thoughtless act. On the contrary, we live in an age of seamless political ideological absence in which thoughtless violence finds its place in newer forms. However, the persistence of this mode is even stronger than before, by intruding into the everyday forms of existence. This kind of thoughtlessness is bringing forth even more devastating effects [no longer invisible] by the pathology of indispensability. Thoughtlessness has another sense to it. Failure to act even when one is perceptive (banality) about the loss, harm or tragic consequences of actions magnifies moral blameworthiness. Current democracies resonate in such a situation. This puts Arendt's belief in democracy and political power in jeopardy. Risked is her sense of human plurality as the grounding principle of a political society. It also risks thinking as a faculty of everyday life because everybody does not think. This affects our collective action. Individuals are always influenced by others' beliefs and actions, even acts of violence.

Combating thoughtlessness itself is a futile exercise for reasonable individuals will find it impossible to achieve. Here, we are talking about the reconciliation of differences; these differences are not supposed to be but are matters of fact. Irreconciliation keeps two aspects alive: thoughtlessness and violence. As long as one individual continues to follow another because of specific attributes, Arendt's idea of "thinking" remains relevant.¹⁰ What kind of conscience can we build amid such indifference? Building that conscience is directly linked to the scale of everyday violence. Schiff is correct in arguing that stories can thwart progressive politics, and, to a great extent, generate thoughtlessness. This can be very relatable to societies with a very complex social milieu and not-so-rationalistic politics (like India).¹¹ In this sense, the narration-reception of the past becomes one of the prime causes of modern political violence. It has been challenging the emergence of radical democracies. Distortion of conscience has become an important issue here.

This irreconcilability even defeats Honneth's theory of recognition, which stresses the intersubjective view of identity, the 'advent of social orders of recognition,'¹² and a moral interpretation of conflict. Irreconcilability results from the complete disrespect of certain (historical) identities, communities,

⁹ Jacob Schiff, "The Varieties of Thoughtlessness and Limits of Thinking," *European Journal of Political Theory*, 12.2, 2012, 99-115.

¹⁰ Schiff notes that "societies can become conscious of their past through narrative ... revising accounts of our past to construct a moral conscience – embedded in the moral image of the world ... to produce institutions ... to exercise judgment." (Maria Dia Lara) The importance of the narrative in shaping political life is an issue that can be discussed elsewhere. We are making the point that the reception of the narrative is equally essential to telling the narrative.

¹¹ The risks of narrative engagement have become more significant as these narratives themselves trigger futile provocations and even lead to violent dehumanization. The significant element in the narrative engagement is the dialectical play of narrative stories.

¹² Genel, Katia & Jean-Philippe Deranty, *Recognition or Disagreement: A Critical Encounter on the Politics of Freedom and Equality* [New Directions in Critical Theory], New York, Columbia University Press, 2016.

groups, cultures, and beliefs in the ladder of the social order (like caste-based and religion-based reconciliations in India). Ranciere's point is closer to our argument: we need to discuss reconciliation while valuing disagreement and the "murkiness of inherent violence" or "irreducible differences." This is a greater possibility instead. Honneth's claim of the normativity of social orders found in the actual experiences of injustice indeed provides answers to some dilemmas of political liberalism.¹³ However, the worry is for those radical asymmetries and suppressed differences that even a robust civil-political democratic law fails to preserve. The radically different other is forced to live the way of the imposer, where the latter boldly imposes her strong sense of moral right onto the victim. Adverse scenarios arise when political rights determine moral rights. Arendt had a different and a deeper philosophical account of thinking that involved critical self-reflection, bringing caution to human actions. Besides, thinking is accompanied by judgment – at least, this was the belief of Arendt.

The real task is to understand the normalized exceptions, their violent tendencies, and which one to respond to while 'letting others pass' the moment. The above situation may imply that we are still at the beginning point of comprehending fundamental violence while messing up with 'violence becoming fundamental.' In other words, we are supposed to justify other violence (political) in the shadow of an immanent condition of violence. The fundamental nature of violence still sticks to survival politics. Societies and their politics are also shaped by this concern. Its continued presence brings us more problems, preventing us from experiencing the reconciliation and recognition that Honneth and others were discussing. The question is, 'survival as what?' It is more about manifesting this as a condition shaping the human world. The social order translated the ideas of fundamental normative violence (symbolic violence) and empirical violence (physical violence). In a different way, like Derridean originary violence, it indicates the beginnings of violence. The exciting part is the difference seen in Hobbesian precarious natural conditions and the Derridean understanding of the same in the social lives of individuals.

II.

Opposition to foundationalism or rejection of banisters also indicates that "theory and politics are incompatible concepts. Whereas politics is at the same time plural, particular, and contingent, theory is always grasping at something universal, abstract, and stable."¹⁴ Bruno Bosteels asks a fascinating question: "What happens when violence is placed at the root of the social bond?" He makes an excellent discussion of this question in terms of ontological, metaphysical and in terms of specific moments of violence. Bosteels asks more questions here: "What happens when the notion of violent antagonism becomes generalized as a ubiquitous and original fact of social life? What are the consequences of casting the argument in terms of an ontological or metaphysical kind of violence that we disallow at our peril no less than others?"¹⁵ All these questions that Bruno Bosteels raises are so vital that they delve into originary violence, metaphysical violence, and everyday violence. Of all the questions mentioned above, the question of violence as an ubiquitous social fact worries us the most. Violence is an ubiquitous social fact

¹³Deranty, Jean-Philippe Deranty, "Injustice, Violence and Social Struggle: The Critical Potential of Axel Honneth's Theory of Recognition," *Critical Horizons*, 5.1, 2004, 297–322.

¹⁴ Chris Kennedy, "The Future of Political Theory: Revisiting its Past and Some Thoughts About its Future," *Humanities Futures The Future of Political Theory: Revisiting Its Past and Some Thoughts About Its Future* - Franklin Humanities Institute (humanitiesfutures.org)

¹⁵ Bosteels, Bruno. "Critique of Originary Violence: Freud, Heidegger, Derrida." *The Undecidable Unconscious: A Journal of Deconstruction and Psychoanalysis*, vol. 4, 2017, p. 27-66. *Project MUSE*, doi:10.1353/ujd.2017.0001.

by the virtue of overt and covert forms of exercise of discrimination, forced discrimination, explicit violence, and, to use Agamben's words – "killing with impunity."¹⁶ Everyday violence can also be critiqued here, although this phrase is brought forth to explain international crimes, crimes against humanity, and the condition of stateless people. Fearlessness of the law and the law's abandonment (political ban) expose the vulnerable to sovereign violence. Jessica Whyte names it "a person's killability (easy 'injury to others')."¹⁷ These indicate the fragility of the social bond itself – where groups and individuals are obsessed by instinctual drives of power and dominance. Vulnerability also remains as ever present when *some* individuals are out of the law's gaze, posing threats to the 'preservation of life' of others that the law itself claims to guarantee. This has varied forms in the non-Western world – especially the ethnic strife in Africa and the caste atrocities and religious antagonisms in India. Such vulnerability makes us remain witness to everyday atrocities like caste violence in India not seen as substantially challenging democratic values. Ubiquity means that metaphysical violence has become the regulative condition of the social order. Arendt's interpretation of violence refuted totalitarian systems looking toward democracy. Ironically, the kind of violence discussed here has been happening in democratic political cultures themselves. David Spitz made an interesting observation in this regard. He stated that the functioning of democratic states is always found in the mode of abuse of power. Moreover, it happens in the shadow of injustice.¹⁸ The law's authority and sovereign power [*sovereign* excesses] are to be questioned when they fail to be objective in their exercise of responsibilities. Otherwise, such instances are nothing but acts of political abuse. They are experienced in democracy only when the non-political confiscates the political and the juridical.

The abuses of the political system are to be taken very seriously. The abuse of political power is abuse of the people. Why do authoritarian tendencies take over cultures of democracy within democratic orders? Why do people hand over political power to such tendencies?¹⁹ Normalized exceptions resemble the corruption of the political system but also reflect the nature of the civil order in which the actual inequality resides. It reflects the relationships of individuals belonging to different layers of social hierarchy. The Abuse of power also takes place here while the continuation of these hierarchies is sought vehemently. Besides, the fundamental recognition of the social and political orders determines the nature of these orders. Continued forms of existence are seen in emphatic forms of power, dominance, and violence. There is a clever stance of certain Western political philosophers – "the ubiquity of violence" and the destructive engagement of antagonisms as the constituent determinants of the social bond refer to something fundamental to our existence. How is this possibility conceived? The implications of fundamental violence are immensely complicated. The condition of the social makes constant efforts to shape political institutions (politics) that also take note of the political (speaking in terms of the Aristotelian political animal). The contestations of the political (like Ranciere's "Dissensus") intrude into politics, challenging the integrity of the latter. Excesses of law, sovereignty, and the order of politics create

¹⁶ Agamben, Giorgio. 1998. *Homo Sacer: Sovereign, Power and Bare life*. Stanford: Stanford University Press. p. 6.

¹⁷ Jessica Whyte, *Catastrophe and Redemption*, Albany: State University of Washington Press, 2013.

¹⁸ David Spitz, "On the Abuses of Power in Democratic States," *Midwest Journal of Political Science*, 1.3/4, 1957, 225-232. Robert Post explained the ambiguous relationship between democracy and equality in his article "Democracy and Equality," *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* [Special issue on "Law, Society and Democracy: Comparative Perspectives"], 603, Jan 2006, 24-36.

¹⁹ Elena Cherapanov, "Abuse of Political Power is the Abuse of People: When are we going to stop Re-electing Dictators?" *Transforming Society*, <https://www.transformingsociety.co.uk/2023/01/27/abuse-of-political-power-is-the-abuse-of-people-when-are-we-going-to-stop-re-electing-dictators/> [27th January 2023]

the condition of a permanent exception. When violence is ontological and fundamental, it appears in every domain of human activity – from abstract determinants to specific forms. This recognition must identify permissible and impermissible violence.

Violence and social contract philosophy face a peculiar paradox - the creation of civil and political society indicates not just the relinquishing of primordality (like the Freudian primal crime), but humans evolve as sentient beings, and this affects their collective life. A philosophical supposition here meets historical facts traditional, modern and contemporary. The emergent aspect of this intersection is the changing sense of politics. To understand this, we need to understand the anthropological dimension of the collective lives of individuals. For instance, Bosteels discusses Schmitt's thesis, which signifies that "there is an insertable degree of antagonism that keeps society from becoming a self-transparent whole."²⁰ The fundamental violence makes many things fundamental. The ubiquity of fundamental violence runs through historical time, making it a historical account, too. Politics today is not faced with fundamental violence and survival concerns alone. More than this, its obligation is to respond to multifarious manifestations of violence resulting from sovereign excesses causing a permanent state of exception. The relevance of politics is challenged by the increasing scale of insidious violence inflicted on the vulnerable [*in the name of ...*]. Civility has become an impossible reality amid radical political differences and diverse social conditions. Etienne Balibar makes an apt remark :- "ultra-obsession with one's identities."²¹

Fear of a permanent state of exception is similar to Balibar's idea of "return of the repressed," – opening the floodgates of "natural violence," but concerning the actual instances of the world. The right to use violence still lies in the centers of power [multiple monopolies²² (other than the state)] of the social hierarchy where, to speak in the Marxian way; it still lies with the ruling class that occupies the state power. It acquires dangerous legitimacy as it purports its political righteousness for violence, discrimination, annihilation, hatred, and social disrespect. We can label this potential violence as the return of the condition of natural violence, but not give it a complete sense. It has to be used metaphorically or in what Derrida calls a "figurative" sense. Derrida rightly points out that "acts of nature do not give rise to judgment."²³ Then, the difference between natural violence and violence in the state of law is essential. The transition ("convertibility")²⁴ can be seen from 'anyone against anyone' to 'someone against someone' – 'targeted violence'. Derrida's thesis directs us to a judgmental account of understanding systemic or genocidal violence or crimes against humanity. However, it is unclear whether his perspective helps measure the violence we have been discussing here. The apprehension that judging certain acts is either futile or impossible is clear. However, it will be adverse to overlook judgment in the

²⁰ Bosteels, Bruno. "Critique of Originary Violence: Freud, Heidegger, Derrida." *The Undecidable Unconscious: A Journal of Deconstruction and Psychoanalysis*, vol. 4, 2017, p. 27-66. *Project MUSE*, doi:10.1353/ujd.2017.0001.

²¹ Balibar provides a critical account of Hobbes's articulation of violence and politics – the former attributed to the state of nature and the latter to the state of law. He says that in the Hobbesian way, politics quits the field of violence. Balibar also indicates the ambiguity in human predicaments caught between violence and peace, mainly between the two states of nature and of the law. He also makes a very vital observation of competition between individuals and, more importantly, between associations of individuals in terms of "struggle unto death for recognition." See his book *Violence and Civility: On the Limits of Political Philosophy*, Td., G.M. Goshgarian, New York, Columbia University Press, 2015, pp. 29-32. Also see "Violence and Civility: On the Limits of Political Anthropology," *Differences: A Journal of Feminist Culture Studies*, 20.2 & 5, 2009,

²² From the beginning of the paper, violence is not discussed as state violence *per se*, where the state bulldozes all other violence, trying to monopolize it. Rather, it is posited as a form of dehumanization where an injury is inflicted on the vulnerable, consequent to the non-political confiscation of the political. This violence, as stated earlier, is both normative and physical in nature. It can take the shape of state violence upon capturing the power.

²³ Rick Parrish, "Derrida's Economy of Violence and Hobbes's Social Contract," *Theory & Event*, 7.4, 2005.

²⁴ Balibar, *Violence and Civility*, Chapter 3, "Inconvertible Violence," 74.

name of ‘impossibility to respond to every thoughtlessness.’ Everyday violence is not seen in the sense of natural violence, which suspends our ability to judge it. Besides, everything about it cannot be thought of as ‘let it pass the moment.’

Sovereign and law’s excesses cause the indistinction between political and non-political forms. This indistinction makes the conversion from normative violence to physical violence possible. The desire for a particular kind of social existence free from ever-increasing hatred and antagonisms still lies with us even in the post-foundational scenario. The latter is represented as the absent ground of politics without any absolutist ontology and no determinate politics.²⁵ This has to be marked emphatically. Mouffe and Laclau see antagonisms as independent of the class struggle and the inevitability of the ineradicability of antagonisms. A deeper understanding of social antagonism is required here:– “radical politics without the definition of all adversaries” is unthinkable. Antagonism also translates into fearless social violence out-of-political control. In this argument of Mouffe and Laclau, the social is only a partial effort to construct a society where antagonism is nothing but an impossibility of the limit of the social. The furthest implication of this is that the limit of the social is not the cause of extreme violence. In that case, it is the outcome of the institutions built upon the limits of the social. One widely recognized or commendable work is the Rawlsian idea of justice and a fair society. His theory has a residue (it is worth mentioning Rawls here, though his primary and secondary concerns have nothing to do with violence)²⁶. Political philosophers require another perspective on violence other than making a judgment of the human condition in terms of specific violence and specific crimes. There is an argument of circularity here. We are obligated to address specific acts of violence while unconsciously redirecting our argument to ontological and metaphysical conditions explained. The contradiction lies here – the primordial violence explains the possibility of all other violence because it is in our instincts. This becomes an epistemological problem of brute reductionism, yet, undeniable. The orders of the world and the several historical struggles for social emancipation bear or continue to bear witness to the perpetuation of crimes indicative of growing violations of values of freedom, equality, and justice.

Survival politics and fear of existence (induced mostly) distances us from the morality of human action. Bosteels brings up another point: He seems to locate an anti-Hobbes in Freud’s thought. The violence (a war of all against all) that human beings eschew before entering into social formations seems to be waiting

²⁵ Radical democratic thinkers associate themselves with various versions of post-foundationalism. There is a paradox in the metaphysical departure that brought forth extreme claims to post-metaphysical thinking and anti-foundationalist assertions. It is supposed to have highlighted a political ontology without *arkhe* and an ontology “without ground.” It is about ontological concerns of the way a society is constituted. Post-foundationalism constitutes both quasi-transcendental claims and a total refutation of transcendental politics. Groundless politics embraces radical differences and disagreement [like dissensus] around which a new political community is organized purely non-doctrinal. Even more significant is the emphasis on radical plurality without a “common view of the world.” The political is resided in the radical contingency of being intending to challenge *determinate* social inequalities with embodied social relations. Post-foundationalists paint a new political community in a new shell altogether, with none possessing the right to rule. The world will be rid of totalitarian tendencies fostering democratic culture. They also place politics in an independent realm of its own – independent even from the features of the social. Post-foundationalism is faced with the monumental task of keeping agonism, equality, and socio-political transformation perfectly balanced. All this is wishful thinking as they opine that agonism is a tonic to antagonism. However, global violence seems to have become a regular affair, questioning the metaphysical refutation of post-foundationalism. Mathijs van de Sande, *Prefigurative Democracy: Protest, Social Movements and the Political Institution of Society*, Edinburgh, Edinburgh University Press, 2023. Lois McNay, *The Misguided search for the Political: Social Weightlessness in Radical Democratic Theory*, Cambridge, Polity, 2014. David Matijasevich, *Radical Democracy and its Limits*, Palgrave Macmillan, 2019. Bruno Bosteels, *The Actuality of Communism*, New York, Verso, 2011. George Kateb, “The Adequacy of the Canon,” *Political Theory*, 30.4, Aug 2002, 482-505.

²⁶ John Rawls, *Political Liberalism*, New York, Columbia University Press, 1993.

for us at the end of the road. It is a kind of admonition questioning the human affairs. It requires more severe explanation and critical reflection. The difference between Hobbes and Freud can be seen in this way: in Hobbes's case, self-preservation drives us to free ourselves from ontological (originary) violence. On the contrary, Freud said that there is no escape from this symbolic order. These two combine together fixing our attention on both political and symbolical. Arendt's distinction between power and violence is valid only in the light of reflection on violence and totalitarian systems. The same experience can be seen in various forms of democracy. The reason can be located in the presence of fundamental violence. Balibar's point can be brought here for support. He claims that "...the picture of the condition of violence yields to that of a condition of violence we do not know how to leave..."²⁷ This is true because societies all over aren't clear about the nature of their political orders. Freud point of 'no escape from this symbolic violence' is going to stay with us. The point is our intelligent ways to tackle it by political means when they are irresolvable through social and cultural forms. The latter sanctifies several 'givens' that we are supposed to treat as determinate occurrences and normal. The workings of political order are not grounded in or confined to the unavoidable facts of human nature. When we say the workings of the political order are not merely driven by human nature [Linda Zarelli] [of instincts], it means that there is the profound possibility to overcome, in Kantian terms, the weakness of the will.²⁸ This may place high value on utopian pursuits. The scare of the socialist experiment reminds us of our impossibilities too. However, democracy did not make it better. Cruelty and dehumanization intensified, exposing the failure of human moral capabilities. The status of the human condition can be measured here in terms of the conditions of everyday life. There has to be a convincing explanation for why individuals do not want to treat individuals as "ends-in-themselves."

The two contrasting pictures confuse us, keeping us indecisive between immanent violence [violence as fundamental] and the permeating potentialities of individuals. It seems individuals have no escape from this symbolic violence.²⁹ Symbolic violence sanctifies several 'givens' that we are supposed to treat as determinate occurrences and normal. Much transformation has occurred in our ability to harm or kill with more sophisticated cultures, societies, and politics. Bosteels raises a concern, asking, "When do humans become more than human animals?"³⁰ The truth of survivalist politics is essential here. The contemporary world cannot be indifferent to survival politics. It also legitimizes survivalism through everyday power dynamics – then we are still driven by those primordial drives. Survival as an anthropological principle and as a political principle differ. Both systemic violence and everyday violence can be linked to this supposition. However, what is our prehistory is also our present. This is the tragedy of new-age democratic politics. Democracy does not gain justification on this ground at all. This is the reality – history has repeated itself – to speak to the ghost of Marx.

²⁷ Balibar, Etienne. *Violence and Civility; on the limits of political philosophy*, Columbia University Press, 2015. p. 3.

²⁸ Kant's thinking on this is about one's duty to humanity. The interesting point is the conception of politics with motivation from deontological ethics. This is indispensable even if embodied recognition is called for to take cognizance of radical contingency. Alexander Broadie & Elizabeth M. Pybus, "Kant and Weakness of Will," *Kant-Studien*, 73, 1-4, 2009. Marijana Vujosevic, "Kant's account of Moral Weakness," *European Journal of Philosophy*, 27.1, 2019, 50-54.

²⁹ As a concept, violence is not one of the critical notions of psychoanalysis. In Freud, we cannot see violence; instead, aggression, anger, sadism, masochism, pain and pleasure, crime and punishment, and fear can be seen in his works. He uses these whole concepts to explain the construction of ego and subjectivity. "Violence in the World of Symbolic Order and Psychoanalysis" <https://ps-europe.org/violence-in-the-world-of-symbolic-order-and-psychoanalysis/> Also see Bosteels, "Critique of Originary Violence," 30-32.

³⁰ Bosteels, Bruno., "Critique of Originary Violence," p. 41.

Even if there are natural inequalities into which social inequalities seek their legitimacy – there are insights that we can possibly draw from this. In the movement from the natural state to an organized society, humans had extraordinary experiences of association, sanction and denial – the emergence and disappearance of things. To understand this, we may have to carry out a radical critique of specific social formations. Neither merely philosophical treatment nor a pure anthropological interpretation helps us grasp the enigmas of association. We need to focus on things that happen amid organizing cultures and social and political orders. The dilemma is what can be done if the procedural aspect of the political order is unable to establish a fair intersubjective public realm. The contradiction lies in our blind faith in democracy’s strength in reasonable treatment of all political dilemmas, like the “endism” debate that brings forth the triumphant claims of liberal-capitalist democracy. The political realm is supposed to take care of all the barriers between individuals. There is a difference between barriers between individuals and barriers between collectives, communes and identities. If natural inequalities are maintained as distinct from social inequalities, social standing cannot be determined by the natural barriers argument. The danger lies here.

Let us return to the initial point. As violence is caused by metaphysical foundations – we are compelled to denounce the metaphysical foundations and enter post-foundational politics. Thinking without banisters is an alternative (Hannah Arendt and Richard Bernstein),³¹ and it has to be brought about to understand the human condition. The understanding of everyday violence (the frontiers of violence) has to be more or less like what Bernstein discusses in his book. He states that violence has a significantly broader concept than that of war – other than the physical killing or the paradigm of violence – extending it to the facts of legal violence, structural violence, linguistic violence, symbolic violence, and religious violence. Bernstein asks an interesting question: “But what concerns me is how the different types of violence so easily turn into physical violence- bodily harm and ultimately physical killing.”³² What is thinking without banisters supposed to do to both philosophy and politics? From the point of view of Arendt, it is necessary to take radical action through radical plurality. Everyday violence is constitutive of people with normalized barbarities, dead consciences, and plastic mentalities. We must examine how good banister-less politics is. The significant issue is not the affirmations and admonitions of Arendt but the consequences of her redefinition of politics.³³ Like in the case of systemic violence, are there perpetrators specifically identifiable in everyday violence? The answer is complicated when there is so much reluctance toward justice and equality (retributive justice). This has caused the further escalation of everyday violence, which is unbearable in nature. We need a clarification here. Bernstein mentions several instances of violence that go beyond systemic violence. However, it seems to be not taking note of the several necessary forms of discrimination, force, and domination that may also lead to some serious violence. Bernstein’s work

³¹ Arendt expresses her thoughts on politics without banisters, emphasizing thinking, willing, and judging. Arendt, too, has a one-dimensional argument to her idea – the holocaust experience is the predominant nightmarish experience human beings would never want. Yet she rightly identified the reasons for such thoughtless actions – the presence of unquestioned and unquestionable spheres and elements of culture and knowledge. Tracy B. Strong, *Politics Without Vision*. Seyla Benhabib, “Thinking Without Banisters,” *The New York Book Review* (February 24, 2022 Issue), R. J. Bernstein makes a very striking argument asking us to look for many other causes of violence than we usually talk about – systemic violence. See his book *Violence: Thinking without Banisters*, Cambridge, Polity, 2013.

³² Bernstein, Richard J., *Violence: Thinking without Banisters*, 11-12.

³³ Jerome Kohn “Taking Politics Seriously,” [Review of Hannah Arendt’s *The Promise of Politics*], *Harvard Law Review*, 119.2, Dec 2005, 639-645.

has a limitation - his arguments are highly relevant to contemporary political theory but seem to be locked in particular events that the thinkers he dealt with focused upon.³⁴

Bernstein discusses Carl Schmitt, Walter Benjamin, Hannah Arendt, Frantz Fanon, and Jan Assmann. Indeed, we get an extraordinary account of violence and the human condition from the reflections of these extraordinary thinkers. These perspectives only form the basis for understanding Arendt's concern for the human condition. Our experience of democratic violence in several democratic societies provide more critical reflection than before. Events on which these fine thinkers pass critical reflections are insufficient for a broader critique of everyday violence. Understanding the human condition and its propensity to violence requires us to ground our reflections as events far from our embodiments. Otherwise, the idea of the human condition lacks a broader outlook. However, this point does not negate the profundity of their critical reflections. On the contrary, it attempts to expand the horizons of thinking about violence. How is it done? Understanding violence (including the political) requires understanding humanity and its relation to the political. Otherwise, the idea of humanity is impoverished. It is more pertinent to complex democratic cultures where there is a reluctance to create an objective political realm driven by the principle of dissensus. It has to take into account our ability to resist force, violence, and compulsion.³⁵ Hannah Arendt states, "The periods of being free have been relatively short in the history of mankind."³⁶

Conclusion

Discussions focused in this paper on expanding our observation and understanding of political violence. All the arguments above imply that we are not just caught in the war condition amid its extraordinarily increasing possibility every day. Permanent states of exception create even worse scenarios of everyday violence, which hide under the shadow of normalization. These distort our attention to preserving radical differences through political means. Here, radical is not an affirmation but rather a negation of the sedimented realities of the ordinary lives of individuals. This is one of the reasons why metaphysics is always contested. We make this point while considering freedom, equality, and justice counterintuitively. All we need is to see the causal connection between more extensive violence and everyday violence that might erupt from our attitudes, fears, and antagonisms. We have also seen that it brings political helplessness as the vulnerable are abandoned by law and sovereign authority despite belonging to the juridical field.

The social and political realms are supposed to internalize the abundance of human life and its ephemeral aspects, valuing radical contingency. It is a challenge for democracy to inculcate and sustain a radical culture in order to integrate abundance into its fold. It operates between possibility and impossibility as this abundance has infinite forms. Normalizing the state of exception topples all our utopian pursuits of "live and let others live." The failure of politics to preserve radical diversity is seen in our ignited fears and seeing fellow beings as unworthy humans. It also creates a reckless civil order where individuals lack mutual self-respect. A reckless civil order does not give rise to a responsible political realm. Accepting the duality of an immature social realm and enlightened politics is also paradoxical. The issue is 'what kind

³⁴ We are compelled to say that most of the Western political philosophers have spent all their time interpreting and reflecting either the Holocaust or/and the violence of the socialist experiment.

³⁵ Basnett, Caleb J., "Without banisters: Adorno against humanity," *Contemporary Political Theory*, 16.2, 2017, 207-227, p. 211. <https://doi.org/10.1057/cpt.2016.24>.

³⁶ Keenan, Alan. "Promises, Promises: The Abyss of Freedom and the Loss of the Political in the Work of Hannah Arendt." *Political Theory*, vol. 22, no. 2, 1994, pp. 297-322. JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/192148>. Accessed 21 Sept. 2022.

of politics can be conceived when radical diversity goes out of control?' It implies that radical diversity leads to intolerance of those infinite possibilities we discuss in social existence. Every day foregrounds the profound abundance of human life. It is a brute fact independent of our acceptance of the same. Both large-scale violence and its everyday presence are the outcomes of socio-political non-recognition of those diverse forms and unanticipated emergent conditions.

The more significant claim here is that we need to stick to the form of politics that has enough backing for radical difference and living with diversity. This has been argued time and again. Unless we realize this, we cannot contain people who think of possessing a moral right to control the physical and mental lives of others. This paper asserts that understanding violence should get into a larger expanding circle, and we must be honest with this approach. It helps us grasp how lives are conceived under conditions of loss and deprivation of freedom (social and political, too). How is it possible that there are two different realms of human existence - the social and the political,- totally contrary to each other? It is not an impossible possibility. The ontological difference between the two is of profound significance to democratic politics. A radically diverse society is constitutive of extraordinary complexity and difference, never achieving reasonability *between* differences. It is a social fact bound to emerge endlessly owing to our inventive forms of collectivization. However, this social fact fails to meet its recognition in the world in which it emanates. Though the proponents of recognition theory see some hope here, it is defeated by its misrecognition and/or non-recognition.

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